

Collaborative Cloud Resource Management and Task Consolidation Using JAYA Variants

Kaushik Mishra¹, Member, IEEE, Santosh Kumar Majhi², Member, IEEE,
Kshira Sagar Sahoo³, Senior Member, IEEE, Sourav Kumar Bhoi⁴, Senior Member, IEEE,
Monowar Bhuyan⁵, Senior Member, IEEE, and Amir H. Gandomi⁶, Senior Member, IEEE

Abstract—In Cloud-based computing, job scheduling and load balancing are vital to ensure on-demand dynamic resource provisioning. However, reducing the scheduling parameters may affect datacenter performance due to the fluctuating on-demand requests. To deal with the aforementioned challenges, this research proposes a job scheduling algorithm, which is an improved version of a swarm intelligence algorithm. Two approaches, namely linear weight JAYA (LWJAYA) and chaotic JAYA (CJAYA), are implemented to improve the convergence speed for optimal results. Besides, a load-balancing technique is incorporated in line with job scheduling. Dynamically independent and non-pre-emptive jobs were considered for the simulations, which were simulated on two disparate test cases with homogeneous and heterogeneous VMs. The efficiency of the proposed technique was validated against a synthetic and real-world dataset from NASA, and evaluated against several top-of-the-line intelligent optimization techniques, based on the Holm's test and Friedman test. Findings of the experiment show that the suggested approach performs better than the alternative approaches.

Index Terms—Job scheduling, load balancing, swarm intelligence, JAYA, cloud computing.

Manuscript received 26 July 2023; revised 4 December 2023; accepted 18 April 2024. Date of publication 14 August 2024; date of current version 20 December 2024. This work was supported by the Kempe fellowship via project no. SMK21-0061, Sweden. Additional support was provided by the Wallenberg AI, Autonomous Systems and Software Program (WASP) funded by Knut and Alice Wallenberg Foundation and the European Commission through the Horizon Europe project SovereignEdge.COGNIT (grant no. 101092711). The associate editor coordinating the review of this article and approving it for publication was N. Kumar. (*Corresponding author: Amir H. Gandomi.*)

Kaushik Mishra is with the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Manipal Institute of Technology Bengaluru, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal 576104, India (e-mail: kaushik.mishra@manipal.edu).

Santosh Kumar Majhi is with the Department of Computer Science and Information Technology, Guru Ghasidas Vishwavidyalaya, Bilaspur 495009, India (e-mail: smajhi.csit@ggu.ac.in).

Kshira Sagar Sahoo and Monowar Bhuyan are with the Department of Computing Science, Umeå University, 90187 Umeå, Sweden (e-mail: ksahoo@cs.umu.se; monowar@cs.umu.se).

Sourav Kumar Bhoi is with the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Parala Maharaja Engineering College (Govt.), Berhampur 761003, India (e-mail: sourav.cse@pmec.ac.in).

Amir H. Gandomi is with the Faculty of Engineering and Information Technology, University of Technology Sydney, Sydney, NSW 2007, Australia, and also with the University Research and Innovation Center (EKIK), Óbuda University, 1034 Budapest, Hungary (e-mail: gandomi@uts.edu.au).

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/TNSM.2024.3443285

I. INTRODUCTION

CLOUD providers may be able to accommodate unpredictable on-demand requirements as Cloud computing advances. Cloud computing services are ubiquitous since they can extend their capacity for processing enormous requests through virtualization technology, which is lacking in grid computing. Because of this, Cloud computing has become popular among many business organizations and research communities. It also fulfils the growing need of end-users by offering on-demand services over the Internet based on a pay-as-you-go model [1]. Services are delivered through different levels of infrastructure, platforms, and software-as-a-service models [2], [3]. The utility of these services is made available by the deployment of various Cloud models, such as public Cloud for the general public, private Cloud for an organization only, and hybrid Cloud, which is believed to be the best of both Cloud architectures [4].

The on-demand need of customers is becoming a serious concern for Cloud providers, who must maintain an equilibrium among workloads. These fluctuating and unpredictable demands compel the server to suffer from either overutilization or underutilization. As a result, it may degrade resource usage and overall server performance [5]. To address these issues, Cloud datacenters must be both secure and scalable [6], which requires a virtualization technique that allows existing infrastructure to expand its dimensions by constructing an abstract entity with dynamic resource specifications [7]. Such a technique adopts an effective load-balancing approach [8] with an efficient scheduling mechanism to keep the whole system balanced and enhance resource utilization. This will considerably reduce the makespan and response time [9], [10].

These two problems are categorized as NP-hard problems [11], [12], [13]. According to the literature, there are limited studies on solving these problems by adopting the JAYA variant [12]. Owing to the wide range of task distribution and the participation of contradictory metrics, it is quite challenging to find the best answer to any given scheduling issues in a timely manner. Because of this, it would be very hard to prove that the method works across heterogeneous and homogeneous settings.

The goal of this study is to find better ways to schedule jobs in these areas for VMs along with a focus on balancing the workloads across the system. In particular, this research focuses on improving the classic JAYA algorithm by using

a variant of Chaotic JAYA (CJAYA) and linear weight JAYA (LWJAYA) to expedite the convergence speed to attain an optimal solution. Among the several metaheuristic techniques in the literature, one of the most standard and widely used technique is the particle swarm optimization (PSO) [14]. Because it is a global search technique, PSO is incapable of eliminating the local optima despite its numerous advantages. When the job count in the problem domain grows, it also falls into the trap of early convergence [15]. Comparatively, CJAYA does not get stuck in the local optima, resulting in a higher rate of convergence. This is because both the best and worst outcomes are scrutinized during the same time in a single equation [16]. A genetic algorithm (GA) is another extensively utilized optimization technique due to its multiple benefits. However, GA has a high computational cost due to the involvement of a large number of control parameters. CJAYA, on the other hand, has a low computational and less time complexity. It is easy to use since the solutions are updated in one step with just a single equation. Moreover, CJAYA keeps a balance between the rate at which a particle can be explored and exploited in the domain of the problem. Unlike GA and PSO, CJAYA does not need the tuning of additional control parameters, thereby reducing computational time.

The key highlights of this research are listed below:

- Variants of the JAYA algorithm, in combination with a policy for load balancing, are provided in order to enhance the scheduling of jobs (jobs to VMs) algorithm and provide an effective method for load balancing.
- To maintain the interests of the Cloud service provider and user, a fitness function is considered by keeping the sole objectives intact for load balancing, resource utilization and makespan.
- To demonstrate how well the suggested approach works, simulations were carried out in both homogenous (varied jobs and fixed number of VMs) and heterogeneous (varied VMs and fixed number of jobs) environments.
- To verify the suggested algorithm's efficacy, synthetic and real-world datasets were used and measure QoS parameters.
- Two tests, namely, the Friedman test and the Holm's test, were applied to see how statistically significant the proposed technique was.

Organization: Section II examines the current state of relevant research. The versions of the JAYA algorithm and the problem formulation are explained in Section III and Section IV. The proposed load balancing and task consolidation algorithms using JAYA variants are discussed in Section V. Section VI includes the experimental evaluation of test cases followed by a comparative analysis in Section VII. Finally, Section VIII concludes with research highlights and future perspectives.

II. RELATED RESEARCH

This section discusses the top-of-the-line literature in the context of load balancing in the Cloud computing environment. A substantial amount of material has been published on

job scheduling and load-balancing issues. The solution to these problems is narrowed down into two primary groups: (1) those that address the issue by implementing a heuristic or metaheuristic algorithm, (2) and those that integrate either two metaheuristics or a metaheuristic with a heuristic one for an optimal result.

The first group encompasses the state-of-the-art literature that exploits the work being carried out using heuristic or metaheuristic algorithms.

Ebadifard and Babamir [17] developed and improved a PSO-based job scheduling algorithm to find the best possible solution for job scheduling using a load balancing technique. However, the algorithm's exploration capabilities were limited by the homogeneous simulated environment. Babu and Krishna [18] focused on improving response time and load-balancing rate (DOI) to achieve high throughput. In [19], ant colony optimization was used to provide load balancing. However, along with insufficient scalability and job independence, the homogeneous environment was an underlying disadvantage.

Dasgupta et al. [20] employed an inefficient GA-based load balancing approach because of low fault tolerance and the system's reliability for heterogeneous workloads. The authors of [21] devised a dynamic load-balancing algorithm that focuses on lowering total cost and power utilization. It exhibits a low fault tolerance issue and, as a result, does not consider other QoS measures. Mohanty et al. [22] used Cloud Analysts to propose load-balancing strategies focused on the JAYA algorithm and explored diverse VMs for job execution. However, these strategies were inefficient in handling dynamically-independent workloads.

The second group concentrated on how to solve the scheduling problem in Cloud computing systems by using a combined method. For instance, Khaleel [23] used a RASA technique for job scheduling and resource management in Cloud environment through the load and the capacity of the underlying resources. The authors in [24] propose a hybrid multi-objective-based Harris Hawk Optimization (HHO) algorithm for task offloading in Mobile Cloud computing. Finally, Thakur et al. [25] introduced a multi-scheduling scheme based on quantum theory principles and a gravitational search algorithm inspired by nature for both homogeneous and heterogeneous resources. However, this approach does not provide an energy-efficient algorithm for a workflow application.

In this research, the authors implement a variant of the JAYA algorithm (CJAYA and LWJAYA) to address the scheduling issue in Cloud computing systems. The pivotal role of the current research article is minimizing makespan, and response time while meliorating resource utilization using the improved JAYA algorithm. A load balancing and load migration approach is incorporated to retain the trade-off among VMs and improve performance at the same time.

III. VARIANTS OF THE JAYA ALGORITHM

This section first presents the standard JAYA optimization algorithm. Next, it introduces the modified versions of the JAYA algorithm followed by the binary JAYA.

A. Standard JAYA

In 2015, Rao [26] introduced a population-based metaheuristic approach to solve restricted and unconstrained optimization problems. This algorithm's main notion is to evade the worst solutions to get the best solutions for a given problem. It is referred to as a parameter-less algorithm, as no specific control parameter is required for tuning before performing the actual computation [27]. Due to its computational capabilities, it stands out from the other metaheuristic algorithms. The position is updated using Eq. (1):

$$X_i^{k+1} = X_i^k + c_1(BEST_i - |X_i^k|) - c_2(WORST_i - |X_i^k|) \quad (1)$$

where X_i^{k+1} represents the updated metric of i at cycle $k + 1$; X_i^k represents the previous location of the particle i at epoch k ; and c_1 and c_2 are two arbitrary numbers between 0 and 1. The term $c_1(BEST_i - |X_i^k|)$ denotes the tendency to move closer to the best solution, and the way for circumventing the worst solution is shown by the term $-c_2(WORST_i - |X_i^k|)$. The revised placement is deemed valid if the fitness value of X_i^{k+1} is higher than that of X_i^k .

B. Scheme 1: Linear Weight-Based JAYA (LWJAYA)

In recent years, several variations of the JAYA algorithm have been described in the literature. By striking the right equilibrium across exploration and exploitation during execution, these variations quicken the convergence process. With this aim, this research also adopts a linear-weight-based JAYA algorithm [28] to improve the convergence speed and obtain optimal results. This variation alters the conventional equation (Eq. (1)) by incorporating a weight factor into the extant equation. Consequently, the optimization of the search capacity leads to a decrease in the total number of iterations and computational workload, resulting in the attainment of optimal outcomes. The primary objective of incorporating a factor of weight into the equation is to expedite the process of exploration by minimizing the disparity between the worst and the best possibilities. The changing or varying weight in the altered equation (Eq. (2)) is used to adjust the searching ability. As a result, Eq. (1) can be improved in the following manner:

$$X_i^{k+1} = X_i^k + \omega(c_1(BEST_i - |X_i^k|) - c_2(WORST_i - |X_i^k|)) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{With } \omega = \omega_h - \frac{(\omega_h - \omega_l)i}{T_I}$$

where T_I is the overall epochs; ω is the weight; the current epoch is represented by i ; the highest weight value of ω is shown by ω_h and the lowest weight value of ω is shown by ω_l .

The total amount of iterations corresponds to the frequency at which X_i^k is modified to assess X_i^{k+1} and attain optimal outcomes for the fitness function. If the fitness value of X_i^{k+1} surpasses that of X_i^k , X_i^{k+1} will be chosen; if not the value of X_i^k will be designated as the new best fitness value. This process continues repetitively up until the endpoint requirement is satisfied.

Eq. (2) calculates the product of the weight component and the variance between the $BEST_i$ and $WORST_i$ values, which

Fig. 1. Success Rate vs Weight Factor.

also includes an indication of the present location. Within the problem domain, ω serves as a regulatory element that governs the velocity of particles and maintains the balance between local and global optima. A linearly declining weight component is considered because an elevated level of ω implies a global search at the beginning of the execution, while a smaller value of ω allows for a local search towards the end. Thus, by excluding the least effective solutions with a diminishing value of ω , there is a greater likelihood of reaching the optimal ones [28].

To determine the lowest and highest value of ω , consider the Bohachevsky-1 and Goldstein-Price functions. These functions are executed 30 independent times by considering different weight values in Eq. (2) with 100 iterations and 30 populations. The acceptable optimal values obtained for the 30 independent executions are shown in Fig. 1, which reveals that the success rate of getting the optimal value for both functions is 1.2. For the considered datasets, the values that give optimal results are 0.8 and 1.6. Therefore, the values of ω_h and ω_l are set as 1.6 and 0.8, respectively.

C. Scheme 2: Chaotic JAYA (CJAYA)

This work is founded upon the principles of chaos theory, specifically the application of chaotic JAYA (CJAYA). This approach is utilized to overcome the drawback of slower convergence of the normal JAYA algorithm. It enables more effective exploration of the search area avoiding getting trapped in a local optimum [29]. The CJAYA algorithm operates in a manner that is analogous to the conventional JAYA algorithm. The main difference lies in the fact that CJAYA uses a chaotic random number generator to produce the random numbers, whereas the starting population is produced by employing the chaotic technique. The tent map function was chosen as a chaotic random number generator in this study because of its simplicity, as expressed in Eq. (3):

$$X_i^{k+1} = \begin{cases} X_i^k / 0.7, & X_i^k < 0.7 \\ \frac{10}{3}(1 - X_i^k), & X_i^k \geq 0.7 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where X_i^{k+1} is the latest chaotic random number generated; and X_i^k is the previous random number. The initial value is 0.7 according to a previous study [30] that suggests it affects the chaotic maps' drifting trends.

D. Binary JAYA

Given that the job scheduling problem is discrete, with binary job-resource assignments, the continuous solution produced by LWJAYA AND CJAYA must be modified appropriately. The particles in binary JAYA versions go in a confined path limited to 0 or 1, which is identical to the assignments of jobs and resources in a job scheduling problem. Therefore, the current research applies a binary version of the LWJAYA and CJAYA algorithms, utilizing a tangent hyperbolic logistic transfer function [27]. This function turns the continuous solutions produced into discrete values via Eq. (4):

$$\tanh\left(\left|X_i^{k+1}\right|\right) = \frac{e\left(\left|2X_i^{k+1}\right|\right) - 1}{e\left(\left|2X_i^{k+1}\right|\right) + 1} \quad (4)$$

The current value of X_i^{k+1} is represented in binary form in Eq. (5):

$$X_i^{k+1} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \text{rand}() < \tanh\left(\left|X_i^{k+1}\right|\right) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

IV. COLLABORATIVE RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AND TASK CONSOLIDATION IN THE CLOUD

A. Task-Resource Representation

Users' incoming jobs are assigned to underlying resources in a Cloud datacenter that contains several physical hosts with numerous technical configurations that are responsible for handling users' on-demand requests. The incoming requests are processed by several virtual machines (VMs), which are the abstract entities of the physical hosts with the exact specifications that are being created to process the parallel execution of the incoming requests. For a given problem, consider a set of VMs as $VM = \{VM_1, VM_2, VM_3, \dots, VM_m\}$, where VM_j , $1 \leq j \leq m$ is the j^{th} VM hosted under a respective host. The processing speed of each virtual machine is measured in MIPS. Next, a set of dynamically independent and non-preemptive jobs is enabled to develop $T = \{T_1, T_2, T_3, \dots, T_n\}$, where T_i , $1 \leq i \leq n$ is the i^{th} job with MI (Million Instructions). These independent jobs would be scheduled to a series of VMs under multiple hosts.

For a given problem, the pair of job and resource is considered as a particle. Hence, each particle in the problem space can be mathematically represented as an $N \times d$ -dimensional matrix $X = \{X_{11}, X_{22}, X_{33}, \dots, X_{nm}\}$, where $X_{ij} \{i \in (1, 2, 3, \dots, n); j \in (1, 2, 3, \dots, m)\}$ provides the indices of the VMs that would be used to process job i .

Every job is linked to a certain completion time, which represents the duration it takes for a VM (VM_j) to execute the job T_i , and is essential for an efficient scheduling algorithm. The completion time should be minimized, as expressed in Eq. (6):

$$CT_i = FT_i - ST_i \quad (6)$$

A job's processing time (PT) is the time it takes to complete T_i by a VM_j , which is denoted as PT_{ij} . The PT of all jobs on a VM is denoted as PT and is calculated using Eq. (7):

$$PT = \sum_{i=1}^n PT_{ij}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n \text{ and } j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m \quad (7)$$

The total makespan is obtained by adding all job completion times together (CT_{ij}) by VMs and is denoted as *Makespan*. The pivotal role of this work is to minimize the time it takes to complete a task, *i.e.*, makespan along with elevating the efficient use of available resources. The makespan is represented by Eq. (8):

$$\text{Makespan} = \max\{CT_{ij} \mid (i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n) \in T, (j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m) \in VM\} \quad (8)$$

Jobs are migrated from over-resourced VMs to under-resourced VMs during load balancing to reduce the makespan and response time. A job's processing time varies depending on the size of each VM [18]. Hence, the completion time of jobs to VMs will vary because of the initiation of the load-balancing strategy. Therefore, Eq. (8) can be rewritten as follows [31]:

$$\text{Makespan} = \left\{ \max\left(\sum_{i=1}^n CT_{ij}\right), \max\left(\sum_{i=1}^n PT_{ij}\right) \right\} \quad (9)$$

The resource utilization of VMs is denoted as VMU_j and is evaluated via Eq. (10). The average VM utilization (AVMU) is shown by Eq. (11) [32], [33], where m is the total number of VMs:

$$VMU_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n CT_{ij}}{\text{Makespan}} \quad (10)$$

$$AVMU = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m VMU_j}{m} \quad (11)$$

B. Load Balancing Strategy

The load of a VM ($L(VM_j, t)$) is the total amount of jobs given to a VM at time t . It is the ratio of a whole set of instructions assigned to the rate of service of the j^{th} VM during time interval t using Eq. (12) [34], [35]. Eq. (12) and Eq. (13) are used to express the workload of a VM ($L(VM_j, t)$) and the overall workload (L), respectively, while Eq. (14) is used to evaluate the average workload (AL) of the VMs:

$$L(VM_j, t) = \frac{\text{No. of Tasks}(t)}{SR(VM_j, t)} \quad (12)$$

$$L = \sum_{j=1}^m L(VM_j, t) \quad (13)$$

$$AL = \frac{1}{m} \times L \quad (14)$$

By comparing each VM's load to the average system load, the status of each VM is determined. It is identified as under-resourced (UVM) ($L(VM_j, t) < AL$), over-resourced (OVM) ($L(VM_j, t) > AL$), or normalized ($L(VM_j, t) = AL$). To bring a trade-off in the overall loads, the few jobs of the OVM should be offloaded to one of the UVMs.

According to the literature [36], [37], before migrating overloaded jobs, the available capacity of the UVMs should be verified, which is calculated using Eq. (15) and Eq. (16):

$$TR_{used}(UVM_j) = \sum_{i=1}^n T_i \quad (15)$$

$$TR_{avail}(UVM_j) = TR - TR_{used}(UVM_j) \quad (16)$$

where $TR_{used}(UVM_j)$ is the used resources by a UVM; $TR_{avail}(UVM_j)$ represents the amount of resources available in that UVM; and TR reflects the level of overall utilization of resources.

An appropriate VM with low utilization is selected for migration using cosine similarity [36] and compatibility [17], [37]. The similarity factor between the jobs of OVM ($T(OVM)$) and the under-resourced VM ($TR_{avail}(UVM_j)$) is evaluated by employing cosine similarity (*angle*) (Eq. (17)). The greater similarity between the pair ($T_i^O \rightarrow UVM_j$) holds for the smaller value of angle. Thereafter, the compatibility (θ) between a job (T_i^O) and all the UVMs were evaluated (Eq. (18)). The highest value of θ means having improved compatibility between the duo. In Eq. (18), the value of α is set to 0.5, and the value of angle is determined from each execution of the proposed algorithm. The value of α creates a balance between angle and resource utilization (VMU_j). In Eq. (18), the $\alpha \times angle$ will give a more prominent solution towards the similarity between the jobs and under-resourced VMs, whereas the latter term $(1 - \alpha) \times VMU_j$ indicates the resource utilization pattern between the jobs and under-resourced VMs that make a trade-off between the completion time of a job $T_i(OVM)$ and makespan of the available UVM_j .

$$angle = \text{COS}^{-1} \left(\frac{T(OVM) \times TR_{avail}(UVM_j)}{|T(OVM)| |TR_{avail}(UVM_j)|} \right) \quad (17)$$

$$\theta = \alpha \times angle + (1 - \alpha) \times VMU_j \quad (18)$$

The Degree of Imbalance (DoI) is a metric used to quantify the extent to which workloads in the overall system deviate from their expected values. It is denoted as the standard deviation (σ) and compared with a static threshold value. It is essential to determine if load balancing is possible through this metric. If the value of $\sigma \leq T_{sh}(0, 1)$, then the entire system is considered balanced; otherwise, the entire system is deemed imbalanced. Optimally, the T_{sh} value is set to 0.8 or 0.9 [30]. Eq. (19) defines the degree of load imbalance through the standard deviation (σ):

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m (PT_{ij} - PT)^2} \quad (19)$$

C. Problem Formulation

The task assigned is to schedule a set of jobs T and a set of virtual machines (VMs) in such a way to optimize average resource utilization while minimizing makespan, response time, and load balancing. The following defines the problem objectives:

⓪₁: Minimize and maximize makespan and resource utilization.

$$F_1 = \frac{1}{Makespan} \times AVMU \quad (20)$$

⓪₂: Reduce the load unbalancing.

$$F_2 = \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m (PT_{ij} - PT)^2} \quad (21)$$

Therefore, Eq. (22) defines the fitness function F for the problem, where a lower fitness value denotes a better position for the particle. γ and β in Eq. (22) are the prominent weights. The prominent values are chosen for γ and β over a set of values based on the significance of each objective, which were determined to be 0.5 and 0.5, respectively.

$$F = F_1 \times \gamma + F_2 \times \beta \quad (22)$$

V. PROPOSED LOAD BALANCING AND TASK CONSOLIDATION ALGORITHMS

A. Load Balancing Algorithm

Completion time, processing time, makespan, VMs' load, and average load must all be evaluated prior to load balancing. The average deviation (σ) is used as a measure of the amount of variation, and it is compared to a predetermined threshold value (T_{sh}) (Section IV-B). If the value is found to be less than the threshold value (T_{sh}), the system is in a normalized state; otherwise, it is an imbalanced state. Load balancing cannot occur if the total load (L) exceeds the average load (AL); in other cases, load balancing must be initiated. Based on the allocated loads, the virtual machines will then be categorized as UVM, OVM, or NVM. Under-resourced VMs are organized in ascending order by the load. If two VMs have the same load, they are sorted by resource usage in descending order. The loads that need to be finished are arranged in descending order among the OVMs. Some of the workloads could be transferred to UVMs to balance out the overloaded condition. For scheduling purposes, the Cloud broker adds the jobs that swipe out of OVM and into UVM to the Unused Job List (UUTL). It is necessary to choose an appropriate UVM for the migration. As mentioned previously, used resources ($TR_{used}(UVM_j)$) and available resources ($TR_{avail}(UVM_j)$) of j^{th} UVM are calculated using Eq. (15) and Eq. (16), respectively. The compatibility between jobs and UVM is measured by calculating the cosine similarity (*angle*) and compatibility (θ) using Eq. (17) and Eq. (18), respectively. After that migration method is initiated for the more appropriate pair. The smaller the angle's value, the more compatibility there is between such job-resource pairs. Then, the jobs that are the most compatible are assigned to UVMs. Algorithm 1 depicts the proposed load-balancing algorithm.

B. Task Consolidation Algorithm Using JAYA Variants

The technique proposed in this work has two contributions. It first looks for imbalances in the system's load, and then it maps jobs onto suitable VMs optimally for execution. First, the load-balancing strategy will be activated if there is an imbalance in the load. Eq. (12) is used to determine the loads of the virtual machines (VMs) after the workloads have been assigned to them. Eq. (12) and Eq. (14) will be

Algorithm 1 Load Balancing Algorithm**Input:**

1. Set of jobs $T = \{T_1, T_2, T_3, \dots, T_n\}$, $T_i \in T$ with the respective CT_i ;
2. Set of virtual machines $VM = \{VM_1, VM_2, VM_3, \dots, VM_m\}$, $VM_i \in VM$,

Output: A balanced state of VMs**Start***for* 1 to n

Compute Completion Time period, processing Time, Makespan, Average resource usage, individual's workload VM and mean system workload through Eq. (6), Eq. (9), Eq. (11), Eq. (12), and Eq. (14);

end for;*/* State prediction of the system */**for* 1 to nCompute σ of workload using Eq. (19);*if* ($\sigma \leq T_{sh}$)

A balanced system is achieved;

Exit;

end if;*end for*;*if* ($L > AL$)

Balancing load is impossible;

End;

Otherwise

Activate load-balancing procedure;

3. */* Grouping the VMs */*

Categorize the VMs into three clusters in accordance to loads: Over- resourced (OVM), Under- resourced (UVM), and Normalized (NVM);

4. */* Arrangement of VMs */**while* ($UVM \neq Null$)

Order UVM by their relative loads in increasing order;

Reorganize the UVM in decreasing order according to resource usage;

Arrange OVM by the load in order of decreasing;

end while;5. */* Migration of Jobs */**while* ($OVM \neq Null$ and $UVM \neq Null$)

Get JobList which needs to transfer from OVM;

for ($job \in JobList$)

Add this job to the UUTL (Unused Job List);

end for;*end while*;6. */* Underloaded VM Selection (UVM) for Migration*/**while* ($UVM \neq Null$)

Calculate $(TR_{used}(UVM_j))$ and $(TR_{avail}(UVM_j))$ using Eq. (15) and Eq. (16);

Find the angle and θ using Eq. (17) and Eq. (18);

Assign jobs onto those UVMs which has better compatibility;

end while;**End****Algorithm 2** Task Consolidation Using Variants of JAYA Algorithms**Start**

1. Initialize the entire set of jobs, virtual machines, and the locations of the elements, using Chaos map theory Eq. (3).
2. *for* 1 to n

Run load balancing algorithm (Algorithm 1);

Transfer jobs from overloaded VMs onto underloaded VMs using Eq. (17) and Eq. (18);

end for;*/*START JAYA*/*

3. *while* ($t \leq t_{max}$)

for 1 to n */* Fitness evaluation */*

Evaluate fitness values with the help of Eq. (22);

Identify the best and worst solutions;

if ($fitness\ value < BEST_i$)Rename the latest fitness number to $BEST_i$;*end if*;*end for*;

4. *for* 1 to n */* Position estimation */*

Evaluate its location either using Eq. (1) (CJAYA) or Eq. (2) (LWJAYA) to produce a series of matching;

Using Eq. (4) and Eq. (5) (Binary), translate ongoing new solutions to finite alternatives to change their location;

end for;*end while*;

5. Deliver the optimal solution possible;

*/*END JAYA*/***End**

parameter in Eq. (22). The optimal and suboptimal fitness metrics for particles in the population group are determined. Then, the position of the particles is updated using Eq. (1) (CJAYA) or Eq. (2) (LWJAYA). The current position is the new best solution if it is preferable to the prior one; otherwise, the prior position is used as the best solution. After generating the potential solutions, the continuous solutions are converted into binary values applying the binary versions of the CJAYA and LWJAYA algorithms, as described by Eq. (4) and Eq. (5). This conversion is necessary because job scheduling is a binary problem, where jobs are allocated to VMs as either 0s or 1s. These steps will be repeated until the maximum iteration is reached. The pseudocode for the job scheduling using JAYA variants is illustrated in Algorithm 2.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL ASSESSMENT

Two aspects for validating the implemented algorithms' effectiveness were considered. First, the algorithms were implemented in a homogenous environment to solve the scheduling problem for a set of conflicting scheduling parameters. Second, the said algorithm was simulated with heterogeneous resources for the same set of conflicting scheduling parameters. The influence of scheduling parameters for the considered simulation environments is recorded and depicted

used to group the virtual machines (VMs) according to their respective loads, whether they are overloaded, underloaded, or normalized. Afterwards, the overloaded VM's job will be transferred onto the suitable UVMs according to the angle and θ that exist between them, which is determined using Eq. (17) and Eq. (18). Once the overall system is normalized, then it will start scheduling the job using the chaotic JAYA (CJAYA) technique. The particles' competence is assessed using the

TABLE I
TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS

# of datacenters	2
Architecture	x86
Operating System	Linux
VMM	Xen
# of Hosts	100
# of physical cores	(3- 7)
Processing Speed	(24059 - 218810) MIPS
RAM	32 GB
Storage	1 TB
Bandwidth	1020400 MIPS
# of VMs	600 (Test case 1), 50- 300 (Test case 2)
# of jobs	(500- 3000) (Test 1), 750 (Test 2)

in figures. With the acquired findings, a distribution-free test analysis (Friedman test) trailed by a Holm's test was conducted to confirm the qualitative and statistical significance of the suggested method over other related baselines.

A. Experimental Setup

The experiments have been carried out on a PC with an Intel i5 processor clocked at 3.4 GHz and 4 GB of RAM. CloudSim [38] classes have been enhanced to do simulations in a Cloud context. To assign the tasks to the appropriate VMs, the datacenterBroker class's bindCloudletToVM() method has been expanded. The tasks are assigned to virtual machines (VMs) using CloudSim's space-shared policy, which is the default. This simulator allows the user to design, test, and explore Cloud services and applications by providing a virtualized environment that supports on-demand provisioning. Dynamic scheduling is used to minimize the average within Quality of Service (QoS) metrics by considering independent and non-preemptive activities of various deadlines. The space-shared policy is used to allocate the jobs to VMs except for RR (time-shared policy). Herein, 100 alternatives were defined as the population for all techniques, and 1000 cycles were set as the stopping criteria. We undertook these investigations in separate simulations to see how they functioned in a mixed setting. In order to make a logical decision, each experiment is carried out ten times independently, and the mean values are noted. In every experiment, the execution time interval is 500 ms. The efficiency of this scheduling system was assessed using QoS criteria, such as makespan, resource usage, turnaround time, as well as the number of tasks transferred (NOTM). The acquired results were compared with those of conventional scheduling algorithms like RR and evolutionary algorithms, including binary PSO (BPSO) [39], JAYA [22], and GA [20]. Tables I and II list the technical specifications and algorithmic parameters used to perform the desired experiments.

B. Dataset Descriptions

We employed two distinct datasets as individual tasks in the simulation to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed methodology. In the first, a synthetic dataset (R_DS) was created, which consists of 3 kinds of job sets. These job sets were categorized into small, medium, and large types with respect to the lengths of jobs. The small type contains

TABLE II
ALGORITHMIC PARAMETERS

Baselines	Value
GA	$\mu = 0.6, \eta = 0.02, r_1, r_2 = 0.5$
JAYA	$r_1, r_2 = 0.5$
BPSO	Weight (ω) = 1, Coefficients $c_1, c_2 = 1.49445, r_1, r_2 = 0.5$
CJAYA LWJAYA	$c_1, c_2 = 0.5$, chaotic random number generator = 0.7, T_1 (total iterations) = 100, $\omega_p = 1.6, \omega_f = 0.8$

Population size = 100; Maximum number of iterations (t_{max}) = 1000

TABLE III
UTILIZED DATASETS

Types of Dataset	Classification In terms of Number	Length of Jobs in MI
Synthetic (R_DS)	Low (0-1000)	[0-5000]
	Medium (1000-2000)	[5000-10000]
	High (2000-3000)	[10000-15000]
NASA [42]	Low (0-1000)	[0-5000]
	Medium (1000- 2000)	[5000-10000]
	High (2000-3000)	[10000-15000]

jobs ranging from 0 to 5000 MI in length; the medium type job sets range from 5000 to 10000 MI in length; and the large type ranges from 10000 to 15000 MI. Furthermore, the NASA Ames Research Center prepared a dataset of three months of activity logged from 128 iPSC/860 servers in 1993 [40]. The database contains 42,240 activities, whereby each activity is classified as a job based on the deadline. The usefulness of this proposed method is demonstrated by employing makespan, resource consumption, and response time as Quality-of-Service criteria. Table III shows how the datasets were used during the experiments.

C. Experimental Test Cases

To assess the efficacy of the proposed approach in both uniform and diverse environmental settings, we conducted experiments on two separate test scenarios.

Test case 1: When the number of jobs varies while VMs stay unchanged, Makespan, turnaround time, and resource consumption all have an impact: Independent jobs varied from 500 to 3000, and 600 VMs were considered to conduct the simulation in this test case. Experiments were repeated ten times, and the average values of the results were recorded because each execution yields different outcomes. The 300 ms interval between executions was chosen. For makespan, response time, and resource utilization in a homogeneous context, the mean values acquired for ten independent executions have been recorded. Figures 2, 3, and 4 show the main experimental results with respect to computation time, capacity utilization, and turnaround time with different numbers of jobs.

Test case 2: When the number of VMs varies while jobs remain constant, Makespan, Turnaround time, and Resource consumption all have an impact: In this test case, a variety of heterogeneous VMs varied from 50 to 300 and 750 jobs were considered to run the simulation. Tests were repeated ten times, and the average values of the outcomes were recorded.

The execution interval was configured to be 300 milliseconds. For different settings, the mean values for makespan, response time, and resource utilization are recorded after ten independent executions. The noteworthy experimental findings for different numbers of VMs are shown in Figures 5, 6, 7, and 8. They show makespan, resource consumption, response time, and NOTM, respectively.

D. Computational Analysis

Any metaheuristic algorithm's success rate is determined by how well it can solve NP-hard problems with reduced time complexity. To assess the effectiveness and resilience of a metaheuristic algorithm, it is crucial to compute its computational complexity. The time taken by the load balancing algorithm is $O(m \times t)$. Under the conventional JAYA method, the time taken to estimate a particle's fitness value is $O(n \times k)$, where n represents a group of particles, whereas k represents the time needed to calculate the fitness value for a single particle. For updating the position of particles in JAYA, it takes $O(t_{\max} \times n)$ time, where $t_{\max} \times n$ is the required time for maximum iterations. As a result, the JAYA algorithm requires $O(nk + (t_{\max} \times n))$ time in total. In the case of chaotic JAYA, the random numbers used to modify the particles' position in the standard JAYA are generated through a chaotic map function. It also takes the same amount of time as JAYA. In contrast, in the case of linear-weight JAYA, a weight factor is added to the basic equation of JAYA. Hence, it also takes $O(nk + (t_{\max} \times n))$ time. However, all these algorithms exhibit the same computational time; CJAYA outperforms the baselines.

E. Statistical Analysis

A statistical analysis was conducted to ascertain the statistical validity and effectiveness of the job scheduling strategies. Friedman's test was employed to determine the significant differences between the tested algorithms [41]. The importance of different versions of the JAYA algorithm as well as other algorithms was examined using Friedman's overall rating. Specifically, the generated values were used to rate the comparable techniques of LWJAYA and CJAYA. The null hypothesis H_0 can be defined as follows: H_0 means every job scheduling functions perfectly well.

The authors investigated three quality characteristics and six techniques to validate the model. Every method was allocated a rank based on its predicted accuracy, which runs from 1 to N_a . The results acquired for each evaluation metric were used to rate every technique. The methodology with the lowest overall number of metrics for assessment (e.g., makespan) is assigned a rating of 1, while the technique with the highest overall number of metrics for assessment is assigned a rating of 6. Given that many approaches produce identical outcomes for a quality indicator, the score was calculated by taking the average of the approach's ratings. For every evaluation metric, all techniques were rated correspondingly. The level of confidence for this trial was established at 0.10. Eq. (23) is utilized to calculate the mean score R_i of the i^{th} methodology.

TABLE IV
OBTAINED RESULTS THROUGH HOLM'S TEST

Baselines	z-value	p-value	$\alpha/(N_a - i)$	Hypothesis
RR	-3.1758	0.03319	0.02	Null
BPSO	-3.5817	0.02572	0.025	Null
GA	-3.00	0.05878	0.33	Null
JAYA	-3.00	0.05878	0.33	Null
LWJAYA	-4.1248	0.00086	0.09	Null

$$R_i = \frac{\text{Sum of total ranks obtained by the } i^{\text{th}} \text{ algorithm}}{\text{Total number of performance parameters}} \quad (23)$$

Eq. (24) presents the Friedman statistics:

$$F_F = \frac{(D - 1)X_F^2}{D(N_a - 1) - X_F^2} \quad (24)$$

where $X_F^2 = \frac{12D}{N_a(N_a+1)} [\sum_{i=1}^6 R_i^2 - \frac{N_a(N_a+1)^2}{4}]$ where N_a is the number of approaches; and D is the total number of evaluation metrics.

The degree of flexibility determines the dispersion of the Friedman statistics F_F , i.e., F -distribution with $(N_a - 1)$ along with $(N_a - 1)(D - 1)$. Six techniques and three performance indicators have a degree of independence between 5 and 10. As a result, the critical cost for 0.10 is 3.29740 [42]. If the scope of F_F is below the crucial threshold price, the null hypothesis H_0 will be accepted; if not the hypothesis will be rejected. The F_F value of 5.44 exceeds the crucial limit of 3.29740 for 6 approaches and 3 metrics used for evaluation. The null hypothesis should be rejected because it undermines the assessed premise. As a result, all of the investigated scheduling methods are substantially diverse and act differently. Similarly, the Friedman test was also conducted for the second test case.

In order to determine if the effectiveness of the suggested approach is statistically better than that of other strategies being examined, Holm's test is employed as an additional post hoc test. Since all of the compared methods are equal, the null hypothesis H_0 is taken into consideration in this test. This test calculates the z value through Eq. (25), and then applies the z value to obtain the probability p from the table of normal distribution. One compares the probability p_i value with $\frac{\alpha}{(N_a - i)}$. Table IV makes it clear that the presumptive hypothesis is not true for any of the compared methods. As a result, it is found that the suggested method statistically outperforms the compared algorithms.

$$z = \frac{R_k - R_i}{SE} \quad (25)$$

where $SE = \sqrt{\frac{N_a(N_a + 1)}{6P}}$

VII. RESULTS ANALYSIS

In this section, an assessment of the outcomes produced from the aforementioned test cases is presented. To assess the efficacy of the implemented algorithms, uniform and diverse resource settings were taken into consideration. The presented approach was compared to existing job scheduling algorithms, including JAYA [22], Binary Particle Swarm Optimization (BPSO) [39], Round Robin (RR) and Genetic Algorithm (GA) [20].

Fig. 2. Performance assessment of makespan for a variable amount of jobs.

To assess the effect of a growing amount of jobs and VMs on the scalability of the suggested approach, we analyzed the performance characteristics using two distinct datasets. These datasets vary in terms of number of jobs having different job length measured in MI, and their execution time.

To assess the effectiveness of the applied strategies, we divided the simulations into two test cases in the Cloud simulation environment. In the first test case, a homogenous environment is considered in which the number of jobs was increased from 0 to 3000 in an increment of 500 jobs, and the number of VMs was set to 600. In the second test case, a heterogeneous environment was considered in which the amount of VMs was varied from 0 to 300 in an increment of 50 VMs, while the number of jobs was fixed to 750. The effectiveness of the suggested approach was assessed against both synthetic and standard datasets in both test cases.

The implemented JAYA variations (LWJAYA and CJAYA) were evaluated based on their ensuing scores for reaction time, makespan, resource utilization, and the number of jobs migrated (NOTM) on two datasets, which were then contrasted with the aforementioned job scheduling algorithms. The mean values of these performance parameters for the ranges of jobs and VMs within the homogenous and heterogeneous environment are recorded. The Friedman evaluation was performed to assess the statistical significance of the techniques, and the Friedman average ranks were allocated to each technique based on their performance. According to the presented results, the CJAYA algorithm outperforms the other algorithms with increasing jobs and VMs. LWJAYA is equally qualified to provide an improved solution and is justified in maintaining an equilibrium across local and global optima.

The following are the graphical representations and the discussion of the results obtained in two test cases.

A. Analysis of Test Case 1 Results

The proposed technique was compared to the existing techniques in Fig. 2, which demonstrates the melioration of makespan by employing the suggested BCJAYA algorithm. The X-axis denotes the progressive quantity of jobs, while the Y-axis in the graph signifies the makespan measured in seconds.

It can be observed from Fig. 2 that when the quantity of jobs is constantly increasing, both LWJAYA and CJAYA provide a balance between loads and, hence, result in a minimization in makespan due to the implementation of an

Fig. 3. Performance assessment of VM utilization for a variable number of jobs.

efficient load balancing strategy. In a situation characterized by a scarcity of jobs, load balancing becomes ineffectual [17]. Put simply, a decrease in job execution leads to a decrease in the number of VMs that become overburdened. As the number of jobs increases, the proposed algorithm outperforms competing algorithms. Binary PSO [39] does not have the capability to improve the makespan due to the absence of a better tuning parameter. JAYA [22] also performed equal to BPSO because it does not consider a load-balancing approach. The load balancing strategy proposed in [18] has the capability to improve load balancing in terms of reducing the makespan by dispersing the loads evenly among VMs. When the number of jobs was 1500, both JAYA and BPSO showed similar results. However, CJAYA doesn't offer much difference in values from the LWJAYA. When the makespan for all the algorithms was considered, CJAYA still performed better.

Fig. 3 shows the values obtained in terms of resource utilization using the proposed method. The X-axis represents the number of jobs, and the Y-axis represents the VM utilization in percentage (%). Based on the results, the proposed method significantly utilized the resources well since it is considered a load-balancing strategy. The rate of success of utilization is contingent upon the level of imbalance within the system. This parameter also has a vital role in the job scheduling problem. Resources should be utilized fairly to prevent overloading or underloading any of the machines. Fig. 3 clearly demonstrates that the proposed strategy yielded superior outcomes when applied to the jobs involving the NASA dataset compared to the synthetic dataset. Both CJAYA and LWJAYA perform equivalently in terms of utilizing resources because both are capable of expediting the searching ability by maintaining the trade-off. When the job size is 1000, JAYA [22] is also qualified to improve the utilization, but as the job size increases, it deteriorates eventually. Both variants of the JAYA algorithm enhance the utilization of VMs compared to the other algorithms.

Fig. 4 shows the depletion of response time using the proposed method, which should be minimized to enhance the users' interaction. The X-axis component represents the number of jobs, while the Y-axis component shows the response time in seconds. The JAYA variants have significantly reduced reaction times as a result of reducing makespan and maximizing VM utilization. The mean values of LWJAYA and CJAYA are approximately equivalent in both datasets when

Fig. 4. Performance assessment of response time for a variable of jobs.

the number of jobs is equal to 1500 and 3000. Because an effective load-balancing method was not adopted, JAYA [22] is not capable of reducing the response time.

In comparison, GA [20] is also not capable of reducing response time due to the involvement of a large pool of control parameters. However, it is evident from Fig. 4 that the JAYA variants significantly reduced response time compared to the other algorithms when the number of jobs varied. The following algorithms’ percentage improvements over the proposed CJAYA approach are listed: 33.81% (RR), 28.35% (BPSO), 21.49% (GA), 13.21% (JAYA), and 4.21% (LWJAYA).

B. Analysis of Test Case 2 Results

Fig. 5 shows the reduced makespan when the number of VMs increased. The X-axis component shows the number of VMs, and the Y-axis component presents the degree of makespan in seconds. Comparing the JAYA variants, BPSO, and JAYA, it is evident that JAYA [22] outperforms BPSO [39] in reducing makespan. Moreover, the JAYA variants show notable improvements in the reduction of makespan over others because of their ability to optimally balance the workloads across VMs. When there are 150 to 200 VMs, the JAYA algorithm performs quite similarly to the BPSO algorithm. Both JAYA variants perform approximately equivalently with not much difference between the resulting values.

Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 present the maximization of resource utilization and reduction in response time, respectively. It can be seen that the suggested algorithm made better use of VMs and cut response time by a large amount relative to the other approaches. Fig. 8 presents the number of jobs migrated for such a set of Tasks-VMs instances, in which the transfer of jobs decreased as the quantity of VMs increased because of the employment of an appropriate load balancing technique. The suggested strategy differs from current methods in that it takes into account the resource utilization pattern and the compatibility of overloaded jobs with underloaded VMs while migrating jobs. The improvement in the strategies for load balancing led to the appropriate circulation of workloads across VMs, hence leading to the maximization of VM utilization while reducing makespan. Therefore, the overall performance of the algorithm meliorated significantly for both resource environments, which are shown in Fig. 2 to Fig. 8.

This research included standard BPSO with a modification in the sigmoid function and a linearly decreasing weight factor in LWJAYA to explore the search space by getting around

Fig. 5. Performance assessment of makespan for a variable number of VMs.

Fig. 6. Performance assessment of VM utilization for disparate numbers of VMs.

Fig. 7. Performance assessment of response time for a different amount of VMs.

the region of local optima. In BPSO [39], when it came to makespan and resource use, just a single objective function is taken into account, as the presented study focused on the employment of a multi-objective fitness function that is affected by makespan, resource usage, and load balancing.

The standard JAYA is applied in JAYA [22] to solve the scheduling issue in Cloud computing. By using a chaotic map value to produce the population, the proposed method, in contrast, addresses the scheduling problem by using a CJAYA method. Additionally, CJAYA is also used to improve the efficiency of the regular JAYA by finding a mix within local and global optima. The following algorithms’ percentage improvements over the proposed CJAYA approach are listed: 33.81% (RR), 28.35% (BPSO), 21.49% (GA), 13.21% (JAYA), and 4.21% (LWJAYA).

Fig. 8. Performance assessment of the reduced number of jobs migration with varying numbers of VMs for NASA.

It is evident from the results that this suggested algorithm CJAYA exhibits a substantial improvement over other contrasted algorithms according to NOTM, response time, makespan and resource utilization using two different types of datasets. Besides, the load balancing technique still uniformly balances the overall system adequately with an increasing number of incoming jobs and heterogeneous VMs.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE SCOPE

This research presents a job scheduling algorithm in amalgamation with the load balancing technique, in which two variants of the JAYA algorithm are implemented in Cloud computing to solve the challenge of how to schedule jobs. The algorithm is a two-fold approach: first, it balances the overall loads across VMs by uniformly dispersing the loads, and as a result, the job scheduling technique could achieve notable improvements in terms of considered QoS parameters; then, it executes the job scheduling using the implemented variants of the JAYA algorithm that employ a binary variant of JAYA. The chaotic random number generator expedites the convergence rate without letting the particles trapped in local optima. After that, the binary JAYA procedure is implemented to turn all possible outcomes into discrete ones. Here, the efficacy of the suggested algorithm was investigated through tests using both homogeneous and heterogeneous resources. The simulation findings demonstrate significant gains in response time, makespan, and resource usage. RR, GA, BPSO, JAYA, and LWJAYA were among the algorithms that outperformed the suggested CJAYA technique. The algorithm's statistical significance was assessed using the Friedman and Holm tests. Given future insight, the proposed algorithm could be improved by combining it with other metaheuristic algorithms. To make sure the algorithm works effectively, other QoS factors could also be incorporated. In addition, this methodology could be further improved to handle the different workflow scheduling problems with varying priorities. Latency overhead could be a challenge when dealing with a diverse range of tasks in the Cloud. A Fog layer or an Edge layer could be introduced in between so the computations could be brought closer to the proximity of the users.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Gratitude is extended to the University of Technology and Obuda University for their support.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. K. Mishra, B. Sahoo, and P. P. Parida, "Load balancing in cloud computing: A big picture," *J. King Saud Univ.-Comput. Info. Sci.*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 149–58, 2020.
- [2] P. Mell and T. Grance, "The NIST definition of Cloud computing," U.S. Dept. Commer., Nat. Inst. Stand. Technol., Gaithersburg, MD, USA, Rep. 800-145, 2011.
- [3] K. Mishra, G. N. V. Rajareddy, U. Ghugar, G. S. Chhabra, and A. H. Gandomi, "A collaborative computation and offloading for compute-intensive and latency-sensitive dependency-aware tasks in dew-enabled vehicular fog computing: A federated deep Q-learning approach," *IEEE Trans. Netw. Service Manag.*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 4600–4614, Dec. 2023.
- [4] K. Mishra and S. Majhi, "A state-of-art on cloud load balancing algorithms," *Int. J. Comput. Digital Syst.*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 201–220, 2020.
- [5] J. O. Gutierrez-Garcia and A. Ramirez-Nafarrate, "Agent-based load balancing in cloud data centers," *Clust. Comput.*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 1041–1062, 2015.
- [6] B. Speitkamp and M. Bichler, "A mathematical programming approach for server consolidation problems in virtualized data centers," *IEEE Trans. Services Comput.*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 266–278, Oct.–Dec. 2010.
- [7] M. Xu, W. Tian, and R. Buyya, "A survey on load balancing algorithms for virtual machines placement in cloud computing," *Concurr. Comput. Pract. Exp.*, vol. 29, no. 12, 2017, Art. no. e4123.
- [8] E. Y. Daraghmi and S.-M. Yuan, "A small world based overlay network for improving dynamic load-balancing," *J. Syst. Softw.*, vol. 107, pp. 187–203, Sep. 2015.
- [9] A. Nakai, E. Madeira, and L. E. Buzato, "On the use of resource reservation for Web services load balancing," *J. Netw. Syst. Manag.*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 502–538, 2015.
- [10] A. S. Milani and N. J. Navimpour, "Load balancing mechanisms and techniques in the cloud environments, systematic literature review, and future trends," *J. Netw. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 71, pp. 86–98, Aug. 2016.
- [11] O. H. Ibarra and C. E. Kim, "Heuristic algorithms for scheduling independent jobs on nonidentical processors," *J. ACM*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 280–289, 1977.
- [12] M. Kalra and S. Singh, "A review of metaheuristic scheduling techniques in cloud computing," *Egyptian Inf. J.*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 275–295, 2015.
- [13] J. D. Ullman, "NP-complete scheduling problems," *J. Comput. Syst. Sci.*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 384–393, 1975.
- [14] L. Xu, K. Wang, Z. Ouyang, and X. Qi, "An improved binary PSO-based job scheduling algorithm in green Cloud computing," in *Proc. 9th IEEE Int. Conf. Commun. Netw. China*, 2014, pp. 126–131.
- [15] G. Kaur and E. S. Sharma, "Optimized utilization of resources using improved particle swarm optimization based job scheduling algorithms in cloud computing," *Int. J. Emerg. Technol. Adv. Eng.*, vol. 4, no. 6, pp. 110–115, 2014.
- [16] R. V. Rao, *Jaya: An Advanced Optimization Algorithm and its Engineering Applications*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer Int. Publ., 2019.
- [17] F. Ebadifard and S. M. Babamir, "A PSO-based job scheduling algorithm improved using a load-balancing technique for the Cloud computing environment," *Concurr. Comput. Pract. Exp.*, vol. 30, no. 12, 2018, Art. no. e4368.
- [18] L. D. D. Babu and P. V. Krishna, "Honey bee behavior inspired load balancing of jobs in Cloud computing environments," *Appl. Soft Comput.*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 2292–2303, 2013.
- [19] K. Li, G. Xu, G. Zhao, Y. Dong, and D. Wang, "Cloud job scheduling based on load balancing ant colony optimization," in *Proc. IEEE 6th Annu. ChinaGrid Conf.*, 2011, pp. 3–9.
- [20] K. Dasgupta, B. Mandal, P. Dutta, J. K. Mandal, and S. Dam, "A genetic algorithm (GA) based load balancing strategy for cloud computing," *Procedia Technol.*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 340–347, 2013.
- [21] M. Vanitha and P. Marikkannu, "Effective resource utilization in cloud environment through a dynamic well-organized load balancing algorithm for virtual machines," *Comput. Elect. Eng.*, vol. 57, pp. 199–208, Jan. 2017.
- [22] S. Mohanty, P. K. Patra, M. Ray, and S. Mohapatra, "An approach for load balancing in cloud computing using JAYA algorithm," *Int. J. Inf. Technol. Web Eng.*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 27–41, 2019.
- [23] M. I. Khaleel, "Region-aware dynamic job scheduling and resource efficiency for load balancing based on adaptive chaotic sparrow search optimization and coalitional game in Cloud computing environments," *J. Netw. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 221, Jan. 2024, Art. no. 103788.

- [24] B. Saemi, A. A. R. Hosseinabadi, A. Khodadadi, S. Mirkamali, and A. Abraham, "Solving task scheduling problem in mobile cloud computing using the hybrid multi-objective Harris hawks optimization algorithm," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 125033–125054, 2023.
- [25] A. S. Thakur, T. Biswas, and P. Kuila, "Binary quantum-inspired gravitational search algorithm-based multi-criteria scheduling for multi-processor computing systems," *J. Supercomput.*, vol. 77, no. 1, pp. 796–817, 2021.
- [26] R. Rao, "Jaya: A simple and new optimization algorithm for solving constrained and unconstrained optimization problems," *Int. J. Ind. Eng. Comput.*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 19–34, 2016.
- [27] T. Prakash, V. P. Singh, S. Singh, and S. Mohanty, "Binary Jaya algorithm based optimal placement of phasor measurement units for power system observability," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 140, pp. 34–35, Jan. 2017.
- [28] C. Pradhan and C. N. Bhende, "Online load frequency control in wind integrated power systems using modified Jaya optimization," *Eng. Appl. Artif. Intell.*, vol. 77, pp. 212–228, Jan. 2019.
- [29] J. L. Ravipudi and M. Neebha, "Synthesis of linear antenna arrays using Jaya, self-adaptive Jaya, and chaotic Jaya algorithms," *AEU-Int. J. Electron. Commun.*, vol. 92, pp. 54–63, Aug. 2018.
- [30] M. Sommer, M. Klink, S. Tomforde, and J. Hähner, "Predictive load balancing in Cloud computing environments based on ensemble forecasting," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Autonomic Comput. (ICAC)*, 2016, pp. 300–307.
- [31] P. Brucker, "Scheduling algorithms," *J. Oper. Res. Soc.*, vol. 50, pp. 774–774, 1999.
- [32] F. Ebadifard, S. M. Babamir, and S. Barani, "A dynamic job scheduling algorithm improved by load balancing in cloud computing," in *Proc. IEEE 6th Int. Conf. Web Res. (ICWR)*, 2020, pp. 177–183.
- [33] K. Mishra and S. K. Majhi, "A binary bird swarm optimization based load balancing algorithm for Cloud computing environment," *Open Comput. Sci.*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 146–160, 2021.
- [34] V. Polepally and K. S. Chatrapati, "Dragonfly optimization and constraint measure-based load balancing in Cloud computing," *Clust. Comput.*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 1099–1111, 2019.
- [35] K. Mishra, J. Pati, and S. K. Majhi, "A dynamic load scheduling in IaaS Cloud using binary JAYA algorithm," *J. King Saud Univ.-Comput. Inf. Sci.*, vol. 34, no. 8, pp. 4914–4930, 2022.
- [36] R. Nanduri, N. Maheshwari, A. Reddyraja, and V. Varma, "Job aware scheduling algorithm for MapReduce framework," in *Proc. IEEE 3rd Int. Conf. Cloud Comput. Technol. Sci.*, 2011, pp. 724–729.
- [37] K. Mishra, R. Pradhan, and S. K. Majhi, "Quantum-inspired binary chaotic salp swarm algorithm (QBCSSA)-based dynamic task scheduling for multiprocessor Cloud computing systems," *J. Supercomput.*, vol. 77, no. 9, pp. 10377–10423, 2021.
- [38] R. N. Calheiros, R. Ranjan, A. Beloglazov, C. A. De Rose, and R. Buyya, "CloudSim: A toolkit for modeling and simulation of Cloud computing environments and evaluation of resource provisioning algorithms," *Softw. Pract. Exp.*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 23–50, 2011.
- [39] K. Mishra and S. Majhi, "Cloud load balancing scheme using binary particle swarm optimization (BPSO) algorithm," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Appl. Math. Comput. Intell. (ICAMCI)*, pp. 1–6, 2020.
- [40] D. G. Feitelson and B. Nitzberg, "Job characteristics of a production parallel scientific workload on the NASA Ames iPSC/860," in *Proc. Workshop Job Sched. Strategies Parallel Process.*, 1995, pp. 337–360.
- [41] J. Demšar, "Statistical comparisons of classifiers over multiple data sets," *J. Mach. Learn. Res.*, vol. 7, pp. 1–30, Dec. 2006.
- [42] "F distribution table." Mar. 18, 2018. [Online]. Available: http://www.socr.ucla.edu/applets.dir/f_table.html